

Mind Reading or Misreading? LLMs on the Big Five Personality Test

Technical Report

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Abstract—We study zero-shot Large Language Models (LLMs) for Automatic Personality Prediction from Text (APPT) under a binary Big Five framing. Five models (GPT-4 and four lightweight open-weight LLMs) are evaluated across two heterogeneous datasets using two prompting strategies: a minimal task description and a linguistically and psychologically enriched prompt, totaling 150 experiments. We adopt a strict evaluation protocol based on class-wise metrics, requiring models to discriminate both trait presence and absence. Across 150 experimental configurations, we find that aggregate scores such as accuracy and macro-F1 frequently mask strongly biased behavior. Only a small fraction of setups (18 out of 150) achieve balanced class-wise performance, and these successes are highly trait- and dataset-dependent. When focusing specifically on the enriched prompt, we find that it substantially reshapes model behavior: while it can correct extreme biases and narrow the performance gap between proprietary models and lightweight open-weight ones in selected cases, it does not provide uniform performance gains and often induces new class asymmetries. Our findings indicate that out-of-the-box LLMs are not yet reliable for binary APPT. More broadly, we show that class-wise evaluation (particularly recall) is essential for diagnosing LLM behavior on psychologically grounded tasks, and that prompt design should be treated as a means to reduce or invert the bias to the detriment of the overall performance, rather than a guaranteed performance booster.

Index Terms—Automatic Personality Prediction, Large Language Models, Evaluation Methodology, Class-wise Evaluation, Prompt Design, Bias and Reliability, Binary Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

We report here additional information and results related to our paper “Mind Reading or Misreading? LLMs on the Big Five Personality Test”.

II. PROMPT TEMPLATES

Templates of prompt strategies presented in the main paper.

Simple prompt

```
simple_system_prompt = f"""You are a psychological text classifier. Your job is to analyze a written text and decide if the BIG5 trait **{TRAIT}** is expressed. You are evaluating the content of the text, not the person.1 If the trait is present in the text, respond with 1. If not, respond with 0. You must always respond with a single digit: 0 or 1. Do not explain or add anything else."""
```

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¹Focusing on the text rather than the individual reduces refusal rates, since many models decline tasks framed as psychological assessment.

Complex prompt

```
complex_prompt = f"""You are an expert in Automatic Personality Prediction using the Five Factor Model (BIG5). Estimate whether the trait **{TRAIT}** is reflected in the style of the text, where "1" means present and "0" absent.\\ Base your judgment on both explicit and implicit cues --- including tone, content, emotional framing, and vocabulary.\\ \\ ---\\ \\ ### Trait Overview\\ \\ **{TRAIT_DESCRIPTION}**\\ \\ ---\\ \\ ### Facet-level Insight\\ \\ If the text reflects these characteristics → output "1": \\ {LONG_POSITIVE_DESCRIPTIONS}\\ \\ If the text reflects these characteristics → output "0": \\ {LONG_NEGATIVE_DESCRIPTIONS}\\ \\ ---\\ \\ ### Adjective Insight\\ \\ Traits associated with output "1": \\ {POSITIVE_ADJECTIVES}\\ \\ Traits associated with output "0": \\ {NEGATIVE_ADJECTIVES}\\ \\ """
```

Complex prompt variables

To ensure reproducibility, we provide all the variables used in the complex prompts in the form of a Python dictionary (Listing 1), to be used with the complex prompt.

Listing 1: Complex prompt strategy variables

```
1 #high-level from Costa 92 NEO-PI-R
2 short_trait_descr={
3     "Neuroticism": "Neuroticism is the dimension underlying a broad group of traits, including anxiety, hostility, and the tendency to experience negative emotions such as guilt and sadness. Related to psychological distress and emotional instability.",
4     "Extraversion": "Extraversion is the dimension underlying a broad group of traits, including sociability, activity, and the tendency to experience positive emotions such as joy and pleasure. High scorers are social, talkative, assertive, and energetic.",
5     "Openness": "High-Openness individuals are imaginative and sensitive to art and beauty and have a rich and complex emotional life; they are intellectually curious, behaviorally flexible, and nondogmatic in their attitudes and values. Related to creativity, openness to novelty, and appreciation for art.",
6     "Agreeableness": "Agreeableness is primarily a dimension of interpersonal behavior. High-Agreeableness individuals are trusting, sympathetic, and cooperative; low-Agreeableness individuals are cynical, callous, and antagonistic. Involves compassion, altruism, and trust in others.",
7     "Conscientiousness": "Conscientiousness is a dimension with social, vocational implications, associated with academic and vocational success. High scorers are disciplined, organized, reliable."
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8 } 73 "Often forget to put things back in
9 their proper place.",
10 "Shirk my duties.", 74
11 #low-level from Goldberg 90 IPIP (facets, 20-item 75
12 scale) 76
13 long_trait_descr={ 77
14 "Extraversion":{ 78
15 "positive":["Am the life of the party.", 79
16 "Feel comfortable around people.", 80
17 "Start conversations.", 81
18 "Talk to a lot of different people at 82
19 parties.", 83 #NEUROTICISM IS INVERTED (the original is
20 "Don't mind being the center of 84 Emotional Stability)!
21 attention.", 85 "Neuroticism":{
22 "Make friends easily.", 86 "negative":["Am relaxed most of the time
23 "Take charge.", 87 "Seldom feel blue.",
24 "Know how to captivate people.", 88 "Am not easily bothered by things.",
25 "Feel at ease with people.", 89 "Rarely get irritated.",
26 "Am skilled in handling social 90 "Seldom get mad."],
27 situations.", 91 "positive":["Get stressed out easily.",
28 "negative":["Don't talk a lot.", 92 "Worry about things.",
29 "Keep in the background.", 93 "Am easily disturbed.",
30 "Have little to say.", 94 "Get upset easily.",
31 "Don't like to draw attention to myself 95 "Change my mood a lot.",
32 "Am quiet around strangers.", 96 "Have frequent mood swings.",
33 "Find it difficult to approach others 97 "Get irritated easily.",
34 "Often feel uncomfortable around others 98 "Often feel blue.",
35 "Bottle up my feelings.", 99 "Get angry easily.",
36 "Am a very private person.", 100 "Panic easily.",
37 "Wait for others to lead the way."] 101 "Feel threatened easily.",
38 }, 102 "Get overwhelmed by emotions.",
39 "Agreeableness":{ 103 "Take offense easily.",
40 "positive":["Am interested in people.", 104 "Get caught up in my problems.",
41 "Sympathize with others' feelings.", 105 "Grumble about things."],
42 "Have a soft heart.", 106 },
43 "Take time out for others.", 107 "Openness":{
44 "Feel others' emotions.", 108 "positive":["Have a rich vocabulary.",
45 "Make people feel at ease.", 109 "Have a vivid imagination.",
46 "Inquire about others' well-being.", 110 "Have excellent ideas.",
47 "Know how to comfort others.", 111 "Am quick to understand things.",
48 "Love children.", 112 "Use difficult words.",
49 "Am on good terms with nearly everyone 113 "Spend time reflecting on things.",
50 "Have a good word for everyone.", 114 "Am full of ideas.",
51 "Show my gratitude.", 115 "Carry the conversation to a higher
52 "Think of others first.", 116 level.",
53 "Love to help others."], 117 "Catch on to things quickly.",
54 "negative":["Insult people.", 118 "Can handle a lot of information.",
55 "Am not interested in other people's 119 "Love to think up new ways of doing
56 problems.", 120 things.",
57 "Feel little concern for others.", 121 "Love to read challenging material.",
58 "Am not really interested in others.", 122 "Am good at many things."],
59 "Am hard to get to know.", 123 "negative":["Have difficulty
60 "Am indifferent to the feelings of 124 understanding abstract ideas."
61 others."], 125 "Am not interested in abstract ideas."
62 }, 126 "Do not have a good imagination."
63 "Conscientiousness":{ 127 "Try to avoid complex people."
64 "positive":["Am always prepared.", 128 "Have difficulty imagining things."
65 "Pay attention to details.", 129 "Avoid difficult reading material."
66 "Get chores done right away.", 130 "Will not probe deeply into a subject
67 "Like order.", 131 "].
68 "Follow a schedule.", 132 }
69 "Am exacting in my work.", 133 }
70 "Do things according to a plan.", 134 #from goldberg 1990 paper, Table 1
71 "Continue until everything is perfect 135
72 "Make plans and stick to them.", 136
73 "Love order and regularity.", 137
74 "Like to tidy up.", 138
75 "negative":["Leave my belongings around 139
76 "Make a mess of things.", 140
77 "companionable",
78
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142      'social',
143      'outgoin',
144      'impulsive',
145      'carefree',
146      'playful',
147      'zany',
148      'mischievous',
149      'rowdy',
150      'loud',
151      'prankish',
152      'brave',
153      'venturous',
154      'fearless',
155      'reckless',
156      'active',
157      'assertive',
158      'dominant',
159      'energetic',
160      'boastful',
161      'conceited',
162      'egotistical',
163      'affected',
164      'vain',
165      'chic',
166      'dapper',
167      'jaunt',
168      'nosey',
169      'snoopy',
170      'indiscreet',
171      'meddlesom',
172      'sexy',
173      'passionate',
174      'sensual',
175      'flirtatious'],
176      "negative":["reserved',
177      'lethargic',
178      'vigorless',
179      'apathetic',
180      'cool',
181      'aloof',
182      'distant',
183      'unsocial',
184      'withdrawn',
185      'quiet',
186      'secretive',
187      'untalkative',
188      'indirect',
189      'humble',
190      'modest',
191      'bashful',
192      'meek',
193      'shy',
194      'joyless',
195      'solemn',
196      'sober',
197      'morose',
198      'moody',
199      'utactless',
200      'thoughtless',
201      'unfriendly']
202  },
203
204  "Agreeableness":{
205      "positive":["trustful',
206      'unsuspicious',
207      'unenvious',
208      'democratic',
209      'friendly',
210      'genial',
211      'cheerful',
212      'generous',
213      'charitable',
214      'indulgent',
215      'lenient',
216      'conciliatory',
217      'cooperative',
218      'agreeable',
219      'tolerant',
220      'reasonable',
221      'impartial',
222      'unbiased',
223      'patient',
224      'moderate',
225      'tactful',
226      'polite',
227      'civil',
228      'kind',
229      'loyal',
230      'unselfish',
231      'helpful',
232      'sensitive',
233      'affectionate',
234      'warm',
235      'tender',
236      'sentimental',
237      'moral',
238      'honest',
239      'just',
240      'principled'],
241      "negative":["sadistic',
242      'vengeful',
243      'cruel',
244      'malicious',
245      'bitter',
246      'testy',
247      'crabby',
248      'sour',
249      'surly',
250      'harsh',
251      'severe',
252      'strict',
253      'critical',
254      'bossy',
255      'derogatory',
256      'caustic',
257      'sarcastic',
258      'catty',
259      'negative',
260      'contrary',
261      'argumentative',
262      'belligerent',
263      'abrasive',
264      'unruly',
265      'aggressive',
266      'biased',
267      'opinionated',
268      'stubborn',
269      'inflexible',
270      'irritable',
271      'explosive',
272      'wild',
273      'short-tempered',
274      'jealous',
275      'mistrustful',
276      'suspicious',
277      'stingy',
278      'selfish',
279      'ungenerous',
280      'envious',
281      'scheming',
282      'sly',
283      'wily',
284      'insincere',
285      'devious']
286  },
287
288  "Conscientiousness":{
289      "positive":["persistent',
290      'ambitious',
291      'organized',
292      'thorough',
293      'orderly',
294      'prim',
295      'tidy',

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296         'discreet',
297         'controlled',
298         'serious',
299         'earnest',
300         'crusading',
301         'zealous',
302         'moralistic',
303         'prudish',
304         'predictable',
305         'rigid',
306         'conventional',
307         'rational',
308         'courtly',
309         'dignified',
310         'genteel',
311         'suave',
312         'conscientious',
313         'dependable',
314         'prompt',
315         'punctual',
316         'blase',
317         'urbane',
318         'cultured',
319         'refined',
320         'formal',
321         'pompous',
322         'smug',
323         'proud',
324         'aimful',
325         'calculating',
326         'farseeing',
327         'progressive',
328         'mystical',
329         'devout',
330         'pious',
331         'spiritual',
332         'mature',
333         'coy',
334         'demure',
335         'chaste',
336         'unvoluptuous',
337         'economical',
338         'frugal',
339         'thrifty',
340         'unextravagant'],
341     "negative":['messy',
342         'forgetful',
343         'lazy',
344         'careless',
345         'changeable',
346         'erratic',
347         'fickle',
348         'absent-minded',
349         'impolite',
350         'impudent',
351         'rude',
352         'cynical',
353         'nonreligious',
354         'informal',
355         'profane',
356         'awkward',
357         'unrefined',
358         'earthy',
359         'practical',
360         'thriftless',
361         'excessive',
362         'self-indulgent']
363 },
364 #INVERTED!
365 "Neuroticism":{
366     "positive":['touchy',
367         'careworn',
368         'whiny',
369         'oversensitive',
370         'fearful',
371         'nervous',
372         'fussy',
373         'unstable',
374         'unconfident',
375         'self-critical',
376         'unpoised',
377         'cowardly',
378         'timid',
379         'unventurous',
380         'wary',
381         'docile',
382         'dependent',
383         'submissive',
384         'pliant',
385         'naive',
386         'gullible',
387         'superstitious',
388         'childlike'],
389     "negative":['tough',
390         'rugged',
391         'unflinching',
392         'wordless',
393         'calm',
394         'stable',
395         'sedate',
396         'peaceful',
397         'confident',
398         'independent',
399         'resourceful',
400         'ruthless',
401         'insensitive',
402         'cold',
403         'stern',
404         'frank',
405         'blunt',
406         'explicit',
407         'curt',
408         'terse']
409 },
410
411     "Openness":{
412         "positive":['intelligent',
413             'philosophical',
414             'complex',
415             'deep',
416             'insightful',
417             'clever',
418             'creative',
419             'curious',
420             'alert',
421             'perceptive',
422             'logical',
423             'certain',
424             'informed',
425             'literate',
426             'studious',
427             'intellectual',
428             'pensive',
429             'thoughtful',
430             'meditative',
431             'literary',
432             'poetic',
433             'artistic',
434             'musical'],
435         "negative":['simple', 'ignorant', 'dull',
436             'illogical', 'narrow']
437     }

```

III. COMPUTATION DETAILS

We leveraged three different machines in parallel to speed up the computation, each one having a Tesla T4 GPU (14GB), with GPU memory per file limited to 50% (peak of 7GB). The computations took about two months in total.

IV. HIGH-LEVEL ANALYSIS OF INVALID OUTPUTS

Invalid outputs per setup

As a high-level and complementary analysis, we evaluate the reliability of model outputs across prompt types, datasets, and traits. An output is considered valid if it consists solely of, or begins with, either 0 or 1.

Table I summarizes invalid outputs across the experimental setups, that is, the number of texts for which the LLM produced an invalid response *in at least one run*. For each dataset, prompt type, and model, the table reports the number of invalid outputs per trait, with percentages calculated relative to the dataset size. For setups with multiple runs, we additionally report confidence intervals *across runs* and the number of runs yielding fully valid outputs out of the total number of runs. Under the simple prompt, most LLMs produce at least some invalid outputs *in at least one run*, with Phi-3 exhibiting a markedly higher rate on the Essays dataset. Failures appear primarily dataset-specific rather than trait-specific: within a given dataset, invalid-output counts are nearly identical across traits, while varying substantially between datasets. The most pronounced case is Phi-3, which shows moderate invalid rates in MyPersonality ($\sim 11.2\%$) and Pandora ($\sim 3\%$), but substantially higher rates in Essays (up to $\sim 80\%$). Other models exhibit low invalid-output rates (generally around $\sim 1\%$ or lower), with slightly higher values observed in Pandora. Gemma (errors confined to Pandora), Mistral (no invalid outputs observed in Essays), and Llama-3.1 display the highest overall robustness. GPT-4 produces fewer invalid outputs than Phi-3 but shows a non-negligible sensitivity in Pandora. Although the absolute number of invalid outputs is larger for Pandora—due to its substantially larger size—the relative proportions are comparable across datasets.

Under the complex prompt, invalid outputs are substantially reduced, often reaching zero *across all runs* for several model–dataset combinations. In particular, Phi-3, which exhibits high invalid-output rates under the simple prompt in Essays, produces fully valid outputs under the complex prompt in that dataset and nearly so in Pandora. However, this improvement is not uniform across models: Llama-3.1 and Mistral exhibit a modest increase in invalid outputs in Pandora, with Llama-3.1 generating more than 200 additional invalid predictions *when aggregated across runs* relative to the simple prompt. A further isolated case is observed for Neuroticism in Essays, where a single invalid output appears under the complex prompt *in one run*, while none were observed under the simple prompt.

Shared invalid outputs

Table II analyzes the overlap of invalid outputs across models. For each dataset and prompt type, pairs of models are compared, and one count is assigned for each text on which both models produce an invalid output on at least one trait *in at least one run*. As an illustrative example, consider three texts and two models: if the first model fails on all traits for the first text (100), and the second model fails on trait O for the first text, trait C for the second, and trait E for the third (111), their logical AND is 100, corresponding to one shared failure—that is, a failure shared at the level of unique texts,

irrespective of the specific traits involved. Here, sequences such as 100 denote binary vectors over texts. On the diagonal (i.e., when a model is compared with itself), this procedure counts the number of texts on which at least one invalid output occurs *across runs*, due to the idempotency of the logical AND. The table further reports the dataset, prompt type, and the compared model pairs. Diagonal values are close to those reported in Table I, indicating that, when invalid outputs occur, they typically affect the same texts across traits. For example, in MyPersonality, Llama-3.1 produces invalid outputs on a small and consistent subset of texts across traits, whereas Phi-3 exhibits only partial overlap, resulting in a larger set of unique failures.

Table II also highlights differences in failure patterns across models. In some configurations, such as Mistral and Phi-3 in Pandora under the complex prompt, invalid outputs occur only on texts that also trigger failures in other models under the same prompt condition. In contrast, other configurations—such as GPT-4 and Phi-3 in Pandora under the simple prompt—exhibit a higher proportion of model-specific failures. In MyPersonality, GPT-4 produces a small number of unique invalid outputs, whereas Mistral’s failures are entirely shared with Llama-3. These patterns suggest that invalid outputs may arise from distinct underlying mechanisms. Manual inspection of a subsample of failures indicates that GPT-4 invalid outputs are primarily associated with safety-related refusals, whereas Phi-3 exhibits a mixture of incoherent completions (e.g., task misunderstanding or verbosity) and refusals.

Dataset	Prompt	Model	O	C	E	A	N
Mypersonality	Simple	llama3.1:8b	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)
		phi3:latest	27.0 (10.80%)	27.0 (10.80%)	24.0 (9.60%)	77.8±25.9 (31.12%±10.35; runs=5/5)	28.0 (11.20%)
		mistral:instruct	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0 (0.80%)
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)	3.0 (1.20%)
Complex	Complex	llama3.1:8b	—	—	—	—	—
		phi3:latest	—	—	—	—	10.5±1.7 (4.20%±0.68; runs=4/5)
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	3.0 (1.20%)	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0 (0.80%)	2.0±0.0 (0.80%±0.00; runs=5/5)	18.2±23.9 (7.28%±9.57; runs=5/5)
Essays	Simple	llama3.1:8b	5.0 (0.20%)	6.0 (0.24%)	7.0 (0.28%)	4.0±0.0 (0.16%±0.00; runs=5/5)	—
		phi3:latest	2002.0 (81.15%)	2068.0 (83.83%)	1978.0 (80.18%)	2093.0 (84.84%)	2069.0 (83.87%)
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	28.0 (1.13%)	28.0 (1.13%)	28.0 (1.13%)	16.4±5.8 (0.66%±0.23; runs=5/5)	28.0 (1.13%)
Complex	Complex	llama3.1:8b	2.0 (0.08%)	2.0 (0.08%)	3.0 (0.12%)	1.0±0.0 (0.04%±0.00; runs=4/5)	1.0 (0.04%)
		phi3:latest	—	—	—	—	—
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	13.6±2.0 (0.55%±0.08; runs=5/5)	16.0 (0.65%)	13.0±1.6 (0.53%±0.07; runs=5/5)	13.2±0.7 (0.54%±0.03; runs=5/5)	13.0 (0.53%)
Pandora	Simple	llama3.1:8b	54.0 (0.38%)	63.0 (0.44%)	66.0 (0.46%)	44.0 (0.31%)	54.0 (0.38%)
		phi3:latest	477.0 (3.35%)	348.0 (2.45%)	347.0 (2.44%)	486.0 (3.42%)	386.0 (2.71%)
		mistral:instruct	3.0 (0.02%)	3.0 (0.02%)	3.0 (0.02%)	2.0 (0.01%)	3.0 (0.02%)
		gemma:7b-instruct	117.0 (0.82%)	73.0 (0.51%)	96.0 (0.68%)	83.0 (0.58%)	95.0 (0.67%)
		gpt-4	345.6±163.6 (2.43%±1.15; runs=5/5)	679.0 (4.77%)	679.0 (4.77%)	679.0 (4.77%)	679.0 (4.77%)
Complex	Complex	llama3.1:8b	220.0 (1.55%)	313.0 (2.20%)	294.0 (2.07%)	377.0 (2.65%)	317.0 (2.23%)
		phi3:latest	5.0 (0.04%)	3.0 (0.02%)	6.0 (0.04%)	8.0 (0.06%)	11.0 (0.08%)
		mistral:instruct	5.0 (0.04%)	4.0 (0.03%)	5.0 (0.04%)	5.0 (0.04%)	5.0 (0.04%)
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	183.0 (1.29%)	195.0 (1.37%)	191.0 (1.34%)	166.0 (1.17%)	441.0 (3.10%)

TABLE I: Number (and percentage relative to dataset size) of invalid outputs, broken down by model, dataset, prompt type, and OCEAN trait. The symbol “—” indicates zero invalid outputs.

Dataset	Prompt	Model A	Model B				
			llama3.1:8b	phi3:latest	mistral:instruct	gemma:7b-instruct	gpt-4
mypersonality	Simple	llama3.1:8b	3 (1.20%)	3 (1.20%)	2 (0.80%)	—	—
		phi3:latest	3 (1.20%)	101 (40.40%)	2 (0.80%)	—	2 (0.80%)
		mistral:instruct	2 (0.80%)	2 (0.80%)	2 (0.80%)	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	—	2 (0.80%)	—	—	3 (1.20%)
	Complex	llama3.1:8b	—	—	—	—	—
		phi3:latest	—	13 (5.20%)	—	—	4 (1.60%)
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	—	4 (1.60%)	—	—	69 (27.60%)
essays	Simple	llama3.1:8b	8 (0.32%)	7 (0.28%)	—	—	1 (0.04%)
		phi3:latest	7 (0.28%)	2146 (86.99%)	—	—	28 (1.13%)
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	1 (0.04%)	28 (1.13%)	—	—	36 (1.46%)
	Complex	llama3.1:8b	3 (0.12%)	—	—	—	1 (0.04%)
		phi3:latest	—	1 (0.04%)	—	—	—
		mistral:instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	1 (0.04%)	—	—	—	22 (0.89%)
pandora	Simple	llama3.1:8b	85 (0.60%)	17 (0.12%)	2 (0.01%)	10 (0.07%)	36 (0.25%)
		phi3:latest	17 (0.12%)	691 (4.86%)	2 (0.01%)	32 (0.23%)	37 (0.26%)
		mistral:instruct	2 (0.01%)	2 (0.01%)	3 (0.02%)	2 (0.01%)	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	10 (0.07%)	32 (0.23%)	2 (0.01%)	123 (0.86%)	7 (0.05%)
		gpt-4	36 (0.25%)	37 (0.26%)	—	7 (0.05%)	565 (3.97%)
	Complex	llama3.1:8b	445 (3.13%)	7 (0.05%)	5 (0.04%)	—	46 (0.32%)
		phi3:latest	7 (0.05%)	18 (0.13%)	1 (0.01%)	—	1 (0.01%)
		mistral:instruct	5 (0.04%)	1 (0.01%)	7 (0.05%)	—	—
		gemma:7b-instruct	—	—	—	—	—
		gpt-4	46 (0.32%)	1 (0.01%)	—	—	525 (3.69%)

TABLE II: Trait-agnostic co-occurrence of invalid outputs between model pairs. Each cell reports the number of texts that were invalid for both models at least once (union across traits and runs).

V. FULL BINARY CLASSIFICATION REPORT FOR THE BEST EXPERIMENTS

In order to have the clearest interpretation of our result, we provide the full binary classification report for both the experiments matching or exceeding the 0.5 minimum adequacy threshold on class-wise F1 (Table III). We also provide details for the experiments matching or exceeding the minimum adequacy threshold on the most commonly used set of metrics, i.e., Accuracy and $F1^+$ (Table IV). This allows us to understand which models achieve non-degenerate discrimination between classes, and which would have been considered good if ignoring class-wise evaluation.

TABLE III: All experiments with class-wise $F1 \geq 0.5$ (sorted in descending order on Accuracy, $F1^+$ and $F1^-$)

Prompt type	Model	Trait	Test data	Support ⁻	Support ⁺	%Class ⁺	Accuracy	$F1^-$	$F1^+$	$\overline{F1}$	Precision ⁻	Recall ⁻	Precision ⁺	Recall ⁺	Good runs	Total runs	
1	complex	gpt-4	O	Essays	1190	1265	0.515275	0.636±0.002	0.654±0.005	0.616±0.005	0.635±0.003	0.606±0.005	0.714±0.010	0.676±0.005	0.564±0.008	5	5
2	complex	mistral:instruct	A	Mypersonality	116	134	0.536000	0.601±0.005	0.588±0.007	0.614±0.005	0.607±0.006	0.568±0.007	0.602±0.011	0.634±0.010	0.600±0.000	5	5
3	complex	gpt-4	A	Essays	1149	1305	0.531785	0.587±0.001	0.564±0.005	0.606±0.005	0.585±0.000	0.558±0.004	0.574±0.013	0.616±0.013	0.602±0.011	5	5
4	complex	gpt-4	E	Essays	1185	1269	0.517115	0.583±0.004	0.544±0.016	0.616±0.005	0.580±0.006	0.576±0.005	0.514±0.024	0.586±0.005	0.644±0.015	5	5
5	simple	mistral:instruct	O	Essays	1196	1271	0.515201	0.582±0.001	0.520±0.000	0.630±0.000	0.575±0.000	0.590±0.000	0.462±0.004	0.580±0.000	0.690±0.000	5	5
6	complex	llama3.1:8b	A	Mypersonality	116	134	0.536000	0.578±0.006	0.582±0.007	0.570±0.006	0.576±0.005	0.540±0.006	0.640±0.016	0.626±0.012	0.524±0.010	5	5
7	simple	gpt-4	A	Essays	1143	1296	0.531365	0.577±0.008	0.478±0.031	0.642±0.007	0.560±0.013	0.564±0.005	0.418±0.051	0.584±0.013	0.716±0.027	1	5
8	complex	mistral:instruct	A	Essays	1157	1310	0.531009	0.558±0.001	0.570±0.000	0.542±0.004	0.556±0.002	0.520±0.000	0.628±0.004	0.600±0.000	0.590±0.000	5	5
9	complex	gpt-4	A	Mypersonality	115	133	0.536290	0.557±0.006	0.506±0.008	0.600±0.006	0.553±0.006	0.524±0.008	0.492±0.007	0.582±0.004	0.618±0.010	5	5
10	simple	gpt-4	O	Pandora	7532	6209	0.451859	0.554±0.022	0.632±0.065	0.410±0.050	0.521±0.008	0.578±0.004	0.718±0.127	0.520±0.025	0.358±0.104	1	5
11	simple	phi:3:latest	A	Mypersonality	104	121	0.537778	0.541±0.001	0.560±0.000	0.522±0.004	0.541±0.002	0.508±0.004	0.612±0.004	0.582±0.004	0.478±0.004	5	5
12	complex	gpt-4	N	Mypersonality	148	96	0.393443	0.523±0.016	0.496±0.016	0.548±0.022	0.522±0.017	0.682±0.011	0.390±0.018	0.440±0.021	0.728±0.020	2	5
13	simple	llama3.1:8b	A	Essays	1155	1308	0.531060	0.523±0.000	0.500±0.000	0.540±0.000	0.520±0.000	0.490±0.000	0.520±0.000	0.550±0.000	0.530±0.000	5	5
14	complex	llama3.1:8b	C	Mypersonality	120	130	0.520000	0.519±0.003	0.520±0.000	0.518±0.007	0.519±0.004	0.500±0.000	0.540±0.000	0.542±0.004	0.498±0.007	5	5
15	simple	gemma:7b-instruct	O	Essays	1196	1271	0.515201	0.515±0.001	0.522±0.004	0.510±0.000	0.516±0.002	0.500±0.000	0.544±0.008	0.532±0.004	0.488±0.004	5	5
16	complex	phi:3:latest	C	Essays	1214	1253	0.507904	0.507±0.025	0.646±0.027	0.122±0.200	0.384±0.086	0.500±0.020	0.928±0.141	0.652±0.035	0.106±0.188	1	5
17	complex	phi:3:latest	N	Mypersonality	151	99	0.396000	0.502±0.003	0.526±0.008	0.476±0.012	0.501±0.002	0.622±0.010	0.454±0.012	0.402±0.004	0.576±0.022	1	5
18	complex	phi:3:latest	A	Essays	1157	1310	0.531009	0.489±0.028	0.614±0.051	0.156±0.208	0.385±0.078	0.480±0.020	0.884±0.188	0.618±0.024	0.140±0.216	1	5

TABLE IV: All experiments with Accuracy and $F1^+ \geq 0.5$ and $F1^- < 0.5$ (sorted in descending order on Accuracy and $F1^+$)

Prompt type	Model	Trait	Test data	Support ⁻	Support ⁺	%Class ⁺	Accuracy	$F1^-$	$F1^+$	$\overline{F1}$	Precision ⁻	Recall ⁻	Precision ⁺	Recall ⁺
1	complex	O	mypersonality	74	176	0.704	0.632	0.220	0.760	0.490	0.300	0.180	0.700	0.820
2	simple	O	mypersonality	74	173	0.700	0.628	0.280	0.750	0.515	0.330	0.240	0.710	0.790
3	complex	O	mypersonality	74	176	0.704	0.620	0.330	0.740	0.535	0.340	0.310	0.720	0.750
4	simple	O	mypersonality	72	175	0.709	0.587	0.430	0.680	0.555	0.360	0.530	0.760	0.610
5	simple	O	essays	1192	1270	0.516	0.579	0.410	0.670	0.540	0.640	0.300	0.560	0.840
6	simple	A	essays	1148	1304	0.532	0.577	0.470	0.650	0.560	0.570	0.400	0.580	0.730
7	simple	N	essays	1234	1233	0.500	0.573	0.470	0.640	0.555	0.620	0.380	0.550	0.770
8	simple	A	essays	1148	1305	0.532	0.573	0.470	0.640	0.555	0.560	0.400	0.580	0.730
9	simple	A	essays	1150	1305	0.532	0.573	0.460	0.650	0.555	0.560	0.390	0.580	0.730
10	complex	O	mypersonality	74	173	0.700	0.571	0.460	0.640	0.550	0.370	0.610	0.770	0.550
11	simple	E	essays	1180	1259	0.516	0.569	0.470	0.640	0.555	0.580	0.400	0.560	0.730
12	simple	A	essays	1149	1305	0.532	0.569	0.450	0.640	0.545	0.560	0.380	0.570	0.730
13	complex	A	essays	1156	1308	0.531	0.560	0.440	0.640	0.540	0.550	0.360	0.570	0.730
14	complex	C	essays	1214	1251	0.508	0.551	0.430	0.630	0.530	0.570	0.340	0.540	0.750
15	complex	O	essays	1196	1271	0.515	0.548	0.380	0.640	0.510	0.570	0.290	0.540	0.790
16	simple	O	mypersonality	66	157	0.704	0.543	0.450	0.610	0.530	0.350	0.640	0.770	0.500
17	simple	A	mypersonality	115	132	0.534	0.543	0.420	0.620	0.520	0.510	0.360	0.560	0.700
18	complex	E	essays	1191	1276	0.517	0.540	0.280	0.660	0.470	0.570	0.190	0.530	0.870
19	simple	C	essays	1213	1248	0.507	0.538	0.490	0.580	0.535	0.540	0.460	0.540	0.620
20	complex	N	essays	1228	1226	0.500	0.536	0.200	0.670	0.435	0.740	0.110	0.520	0.960
21	simple	O	essays	1183	1256	0.515	0.535	0.350	0.640	0.495	0.540	0.260	0.530	0.790
22	simple	N	essays	191	207	0.520	0.533	0.160	0.680	0.420	0.580	0.090	0.530	0.940
23	complex	E	essays	1190	1274	0.517	0.532	0.240	0.660	0.450	0.560	0.150	0.530	0.890
24	simple	C	essays	180	219	0.549	0.526	0.270	0.650	0.460	0.440	0.190	0.550	0.800
25	complex	O	mypersonality	74	176	0.704	0.524	0.420	0.600	0.510	0.330	0.580	0.740	0.500
26	complex	O	pandora	7636	6365	0.455	0.523	0.490	0.550	0.520	0.590	0.430	0.480	0.640
27	simple	A	essays	184	190	0.508	0.521	0.290	0.640	0.465	0.540	0.200	0.520	0.830
28	simple	N	essays	1234	1233	0.500	0.521	0.150	0.670	0.410	0.660	0.090	0.510	0.960
29	complex	O	mypersonality	74	176	0.704	0.520	0.390	0.610	0.500	0.310	0.510	0.720	0.520
30	complex	O	essays	1194	1271	0.516	0.520	0.050	0.680	0.365	0.590	0.030	0.520	0.980
31	complex	N	mypersonality	149	96	0.392	0.518	0.490	0.550	0.520	0.690	0.380	0.430	0.740
32	complex	O	essays	1196	1271	0.515	0.516	0.050	0.680	0.365	0.520	0.030	0.520	0.980
33	complex	N	essays	1234	1233	0.500	0.513	0.150	0.660	0.405	0.590	0.090	0.510	0.940
34	simple	E	essays	1187	1273	0.517	0.512	0.430	0.570	0.500	0.490	0.380	0.520	0.640
35	complex	N	mypersonality	148	95	0.391	0.510	0.480	0.530	0.505	0.670	0.380	0.420	0.720
36	simple	O	essays	235	230	0.495	0.510	0.250	0.640	0.445	0.550	0.160	0.500	0.870
37	simple	E	essays	241	248	0.507	0.509	0.330	0.610	0.470	0.500	0.240	0.510	0.770
38	complex	N	mypersonality	148	96	0.393	0.508	0.480	0.530	0.505	0.670	0.370	0.430	0.720
39	complex	N	essays	1234	1233	0.500	0.505	0.030	0.670	0.350	0.770	0.020	0.500	1.000
40	complex	N	essays	1234	1233	0.500	0.505	0.030	0.670	0.350	0.810	0.010	0.500	1.000
41	complex	N	essays	1234	1232	0.500	0.505	0.020	0.670	0.345	0.930	0.010	0.500	1.000

VI. PANDORA

Pandora’s analysis

Pandora is a particularly problematic dataset. As a first problem, it lacks of an ID column that allows to merge multiple posts from the same authors. In MyPersonality, on the other hand, such a column exists and we do perform the per-user merging. However, given the higher length of Reddit posts as compared to Facebook ones, the dataset presents a mix of short and relatively long texts that makes this dataset worth of analysis. Moreover, due to the lack of binary labels, we also perform binarization. Hence, we retain Pandora as a stress test rather than a crucial dataset for our analysis, showing its statistics in Table V and its results in Figure 1.

Pandora’s binarization

While Essays and MyPersonality already provide binary labels, Pandora requires binarization. To achieve this, we use MyPersonality as reference, given its heavily right-skewed score distributions and derived binary labels. Since Pandora scores are integers in the 1–100 range and MyPersonality scores are continuous in the 1–5 range, we interpolate Pandora values to match MyPersonality’s scale. The threshold is then set to the highest MyPersonality value still labeled as 0 (i.e., not exhibiting the trait), ensuring that Pandora’s positive class corresponds to texts with strong linguistic cues of trait presence. Traditional binarization often relies on mean or median splits. Here, we adopt a thresholding strategy that maximizes the contrast between negative and positive labels. In MyPersonality, the binary split occurs at the peak of a skewed distribution, meaning that many “negative” labels actually correspond to weakly positive cases. In Pandora, by contrast, we define positives only for high-scoring cases, yielding fewer but stronger signals. This produces an imbalanced dataset but ensures linguistic clarity in the positive class.

Dataset	# Texts	# Users	Text Length [Characters]		Text Length [Words]		OPN (1/0)	CON (1/0)	EXT (1/0)	AGR (1/0)	NEU (1/0)
			Median	SD	Median	SD					
Pandora	14221	1608	131.0	438.96	25.0	77.86	6421 / 7800	2512 / 11709	2902 / 11319	2667 / 11554	5334 / 8887

TABLE V: Pandora only — Summary statistics and class distributions for binary personality traits. For each trait, 1 indicates presence and 0 indicates absence, and the number of text with those traits are reported as $num1/num0$, where $num1$ is the number of texts with the trait and $num0$ the number without.

Dataset	Prompt	Model	O	C	E	A	N
Pandora	Simple	Gemma:7b-instruct	0.58 0.43	0.82 0.19	0.79 0.24	0.83 0.19	0.71 0.22
		Llama3.1:8b	0.68 0.35	0.87 0.14	0.86 0.14	0.85 0.15	0.71 0.25
		Mistral:instruct	0.70 0.06	0.90 0.01	0.88 0.02	0.90 0.02	0.77 0.04
		Phi3:latest	0.64 0.34	0.80 0.24	0.80 0.20	0.78 0.25	0.66 0.33
		Gpt-4	0.63 0.4 *	0.83 0.23	0.69 0.29	0.56 0.31	0.41 0.44
	Complex	Gemma:7b-instruct	0.05 0.61	0.50 0.28	0.06 0.34	0.50 0.29	0.00 0.55
		Llama3.1:8b	0.49 0.55	0.71 0.25	0.60 0.32	0.77 0.23	0.49 0.45
		Mistral:instruct	0.38 0.57	0.75 0.22	0.56 0.32	0.66 0.28	0.32 0.50
		Phi3:latest	0.68 0.23	0.90 0.04	0.85 0.13	0.86 0.16	0.74 0.16
		Gpt-4	0.68 0.40	0.88 0.17	0.81 0.31	0.82 0.26	0.68 0.32

TABLE VI: Pandora only — Class-wise F1 scores by model, dataset, prompt type, and Big Five trait. Values are averaged over runs. **Bold** cells indicate configurations where all runs achieved $F1^- > 0.5$ and $F1^+ > 0.5$. Underlined cells indicate, for each dataset and trait, the configuration achieving the best trade-off between performance and class balance ($\frac{F1^- + F1^+}{2} - |F1^- - F1^+|$). All the 95% confidence interval are smaller or equal to 0.01, but for the cases indicated by the asterisk.

Fig. 1: Pandora only. All evaluation metrics of full binary classification report (y axis), per trait (facet columns), models (facet rows) and prompt type (bar color). Bars with a pattern indicate performance yielding class-wise $F1 \geq 0.5$, with a colored frame further highlighting such cases. Background colors highlights the types of metrics: gray for macro ones (i.e., accuracy and average F1) while red and green for class-wise ones (for 0 and 1 labels respectively).

VII. VISUAL COMPARISON OF PRECISION AND RECALL GAPS

We provide Figure 2 in order to better visualize changes of precision and recalls across experiments. While it can already be observed in the figures presented in the main paper, we provide this figure here as a further visual support made ad hoc for this type of observation (i.e., focusing on precision and recall gaps exclusively).

Fig. 2: Evaluation of LLMs according to precision and recall gaps. Setups with multiple runs are highlighted by darker borders and confidence intervals.